

RELAY TEACHING METHOD ON RESEARCH STATISTICS INSTRUCTION: BASIS FOR COURSE ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Many students struggle with mathematics, including statistics, due to factors such as inadequate foundational knowledge and ineffective teaching methods. This study investigated the effectiveness of employing the Relay Teaching Method to improve the students' engagement and knowledge retention in the Research Statistics. The research used a quasi-experimental pretest and posttest design with control and experimental groups. It was participated in by the forty (40) second-year college students enrolled at Research Statistics at Occidental Mindoro State College – Main Campus in Academic Year 2024-2025. Complete enumeration was utilized to identify the participants of the study. The pertinent data were gathered using two kinds of instruments. To identify the level of students' performance in mathematics in terms of their engagement, an adapted and modified survey questionnaire was used. Meanwhile, in terms of knowledge retention, a 40-item pretest and posttest were administered before and after the implementation of the intervention. The study revealed that both conventional and Relay Teaching Methods improved student engagement and knowledge retention. However, the Relay Teaching Method had a more significant positive impact on students' engagement and knowledge retention in mathematics compared to the conventional teaching method. Based on the findings, a course enhancement plan was formulated to guide the wider adoption of the Relay Teaching Method, which aims to further strengthen mathematics instruction and students' performance.

Keywords: *Relay Teaching Method, Collaborative Teaching, Student Engagement, Knowledge Retention, Mathematics Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics improves students' analytical thinking and reasoning abilities. The course helps students develop lifelong skills to deal with real-life problems. It provides individuals with the ability to solve problems and fosters critical thinking, creativity, and personal growth. However, despite being an indispensable course in the school curriculum and a necessary knowledge for daily living, mastery of mathematics courses is not easy.

Mathematics covers vast branches. Statistics, one of the known branches of mathematics, involves gathering, analyzing, interpreting, and presenting data, which is crucial for making informed decisions in different areas such as business, healthcare, and social sciences. The ability to visualize data through graphs and tables further simplifies complex information, making it accessible to broader audiences. In an era where data is abundant, statistical literacy is essential for professionals and individuals seeking to easily understand the claims and interpretations presented in everyday life. Thus, understanding statistics is crucial for fostering critical thinking and serves as protection against misinformation (Bobbit, 2022).

However, even though mathematics is crucial in one's life, there are many students who struggle to learn this subject. Many scholars have considered different factors that contribute to this common issue of poor performance of the students. These involve but are not limited to foundational knowledge, ineffective teaching strategies, and mathematics-related anxiety (Egara & Mosimege, 2024). Primarily, many students demonstrate weak cognitive skills in basic mathematics, which include challenges with classification, understanding probabilistic concepts, and problem-solving. These difficulties hinder their ability to capture more complex mathematical concepts (Gमित, 2022). Aside from student factors, the teacher-related factors significantly affect student performance. The study by Roman (2019) presents that many teachers lack sufficient training and expertise in the course, which affects their teaching methods and the effectiveness of their instruction.

Consequently, the recent findings of the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) specified that 16% of students reached the minimum proficiency standard in mathematics in the Philippines; at a minimum, these students can interpret mathematical situations without direct instructions and represent simple scenarios mathematically. The outcome also shows that 84% of Filipino students who participated in the exam lack adequate mathematical abilities. In the study of Lapinid et al. (2022), the results are not surprising since the mathematics performance of the Philippines has been consistently poor in global assessments.

Over the years, active learning methods have become important in modern educational systems as they foster better understanding and retention of the content taught. Traditional lecture-based methods often fall short of engaging students effectively, leading to a push for innovative teaching techniques that promote participation and critical thinking.

With the alarming issues mentioned, differentiated interventions and programs were practiced as a call for action. On the other hand, as educators, prioritizing the effectiveness of teaching methods in mathematics continues to be a central concern for curriculum implementers. There are numerous teaching approaches that can be implemented to instruct mathematics, with their unique advantages and disadvantages. One of the innovative teaching strategies for mathematics instruction includes the flipped classroom approach, project-based learning, and collaborative learning and teaching strategies (Siller & Ahmad, 2024). The latter is described by student engagement, collaborative problem-solving, and collective knowledge construction. This approach has garnered considerable attention as an innovative and promising teaching strategy to enhance the students' mathematics performance.

The collaborative teaching method in mathematics emerged as a significant pedagogical approach in contemporary education (Stortenbecker, 2021). This is a collaboration of two or more educators to strategize, deliver instruction, and assess the students in a shared classroom environment. The effectiveness of collaborative teaching in mathematics is shown by its adaptability, improvement of pedagogical methods, and creation of a more inclusive learning environment. As the results show, the participants' positive behavior towards the collaborative teaching approach is sustained because they agree that the whole process was helpful for their learning journey.

Meanwhile, Koskinen and Pitkäniemi (2021) indicate that student-centered teaching strategies, such as collaborative learning and teaching, positively affect the students' mathematical understanding and interest. This method encourages active participation and critical thinking, which leads to improved academic performance. Among the collaborative teaching approaches, the "relay teaching method" emerged. It is an interactive instructional approach where multiple instructors take turns teaching different segments of a lesson or topic to students.

Relay teaching is a good example of how teamwork in teaching can help students learn better. This is because it brings teachers together to work, which makes students more interested and helps them remember what they have learned. According to Taban et al. (2023), this methodology greatly improved the academic performance of students since it created an engaging learning environment, which enhanced understanding and retention of mathematical terms and concepts.

However, despite the growing recognition of this approach, its implementation is still limited. This is evident at Occidental Mindoro State College, where most classes are still taught by an individual teacher. In this study, the researcher hopes to enhance the quality of instruction delivery and to bridge the gap in modifying mathematics pedagogy. Furthermore, this research will enhance the existing understanding of the relay teaching method due to the limited available studies regarding this particular method. The researcher presumes that the findings of this research will offer a clear background for this approach to teaching mathematics among higher education students.

Research Questions

This paper investigated the utilization of the Relay Teaching Method in improving students' mathematics performance in terms of engagement and knowledge retention in Research Statistics. Specifically, this research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of mathematics performance of the control group in their pretest and posttest in terms of:
 - 1.1. student engagement; and
 - 1.2. knowledge retention?
2. What is the level of mathematics performance of the experimental group in their pretest and posttest in terms of:
 - 2.1. student engagement; and
 - 2.2. knowledge retention?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control group?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what course enhancement plan can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental design using a pretest-posttest framework with a control and an experimental group to evaluate the effectiveness of the relay teaching method; one group was taught using the relay teaching technique, whereas the other was taught using the conventional teaching method, serving as the control group. The respondents in the research were students from the College of Business, Administration, and Management taking a Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Operations Management at Occidental Mindoro State College, Main Campus. Specifically, the respondents were the forty (40) low-performing students from two sections who were enrolled in Research Statistics during the 2nd Semester of the Year 2024 – 2025. The previous academic record of the student's performance in Mathematics in the Modern World was considered in the selection of the participants of both groups, as this course is a prerequisite for Research Statistics. Students with grades between 75% and 85% in Mathematics in the Modern World course were chosen from both the experimental and control groups.

To gather the pertinent data, two kinds of instruments were utilized. First, to identify the level of students' performance in mathematics based on their engagement prior to and following the intervention, the researcher utilized an adapted-modified survey

instrument created by Flores et al. (2024). The instrument includes 25 statements; students were requested to express their level of engagement using a four-point scale. Meanwhile, to evaluate the students' mathematics performance regarding their knowledge retention in Research Statistics, the control and the experimental groups were both given assessments that consisted of researcher-made 40-item pretests and posttests, which were administered before and after the implementation of the intervention. To ensure that the research instrument was reliable, pilot testing was conducted on a similar group; specifically, it was tested on ten (10) Financial Management second-year students of College of Business, Administration, and Management. Cronbach's alpha was computed to evaluate the reliability and internal consistency of the adapted-modified questionnaire on the students' engagement in mathematics performance. Further, the reliability of the research tool that measures the students' level of mathematics performance in terms of knowledge retention was also tested using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (KR-21).

Subsequently, to guarantee the instrument's validity, the content of the tests was validated by two Master Teachers in mathematics and mathematics specialists with a doctorate in mathematics, having at least five (5) years of teaching experience. The field experts' insights and feedback ensured the accuracy of the tests and their alignment with the intended learning outcomes as reflected in the course syllabus, and efficiently measured the students' proficiency in the subject matter.

Finally, the study utilized frequency, percentage, and mean to measure students' mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention. Likewise, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used to determine the significant differences between the pretest and posttest scores within both the control and experimental groups, while the Mann-Whitney U Test was utilized in determining the significant difference between the mathematics performances of the respondents belonging to the control and experimental groups.

RESULTS

1. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control Group in the Pretest and Posttest

1.1. Student Engagement

Table 1 shows that there is a positive shift in student engagement as evident by the comparison of the means of the students' scores (pretest: 2.41) and (posttest: 2.89). The results show an improvement and shifted the students' engagement from "Not Engaged" to "Engaged", which indicates that the implementation of the conventional teaching positively influenced the way the students engage and participate in mathematics.

Table 1. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control Group in their Pretest and Posttest in terms of Student Engagement

	Statement		Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1.	I listen to my teacher in my math class.	Pretest	2.45	11.5	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.00	4	Engaged
2.	I participate in the discussion in math class.	Pretest	2.65	3	Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
3.	I work hard in math class.	Pretest	2.55	7	Engaged
		Posttest	3.10	2	Engaged
4.	At home, I review math problems that I did not understand in school.	Pretest	2.50	9.5	Engaged
		Posttest	2.75	21.5	Engaged
5.	When I make mistakes in math, I work until I correct them.	Pretest	2.35	17	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.75	21.5	Engaged
6.	I follow my teacher's directions in math class.	Pretest	2.40	14	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.85	16.5	Engaged
7.	I sometimes act out as if I am studying in math class. \mathbb{R}	Pretest	2.45	11.5	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.60	25	Engaged
8.	I am interested in learning new things in math.	Pretest	2.40	14	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
9.	I do like attending math classes.	Pretest	2.65	3	Engaged
		Posttest	2.90	13.5	Engaged
10.	Learning math is fun.	Pretest	2.50	9.5	Engaged
		Posttest	2.90	13.5	Engaged
11.	I feel excited when I study in math.	Pretest	2.15	23.5	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
12.	I feel bored when I study in math. \mathbb{R}	Pretest	2.75	1	Engaged
		Posttest	3.10	2	Engaged
13.	I am excited about solving difficult math problems.	Pretest	2.30	20	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.70	23.5	Engaged
14.	I want to spend more time solving math problems.	Pretest	2.65	3	Engaged
		Posttest	2.80	19	Engaged
15.	I want to get good grade in math class.	Pretest	2.60	5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.10	2	Engaged
16.	When I study math, I ask myself questions to make sure I understand it correctly.	Pretest	2.55	7	Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
17.	I try to connect math to real-life situations.	Pretest	2.15	23.5	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.80	19	Engaged
18.	I try to think of different ways to solve math problems.	Pretest	2.25	22	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
19.	I try to develop my own strategy when I solve math problems.	Pretest	1.70	25	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
20.	I set a goal for myself when I study math.	Pretest	2.35	17	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.90	13.5	Engaged

21.	When I can't solve a math problem, I try to change my strategy.	Pretest	2.30	20	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.95	8	Engaged
22.	I often think about something else when I study math. \mathbb{R}	Pretest	2.55	7	Engaged
		Posttest	2.80	19	Engaged
23.	At home, I think about what I learned in math class.	Pretest	2.30	20	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.70	23.5	Engaged
24.	I am focused when I study math.	Pretest	2.40	14	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.90	13.5	Engaged
25.	I memorized important facts to understand math better.	Pretest	2.35	17	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.85	16.5	Engaged
Overall Mean (Pretest)			2.41		Not Engaged
Overall Mean (Posttest)			2.89		Engaged

1.2. Knowledge Retention

Primitively, the pre-instruction assessment revealed a mean score of 15.05, suggesting the need to improve the students' knowledge retention. Most of the students' mathematics performance in terms of knowledge retention (15 or 75%) is at the "Poor Level," having a range of scores from 9 to 16, while only five (25%) were at the "Good Level," ranging from 17 to 24. While none of the students scored very poorly in the pretest, there were also no students who got a score that ranged from 25 to 32 (Very Good), or excellent scores.

On the contrary, the results of the posttest results of the students in the control group, by evaluating their knowledge retention in mathematics following the study period, indicate an overall improvement in performance, shifting towards the "Good" category. A majority of the participants (55%) achieved scores within the 17-24 range, classified as "Good." Additionally, a notable proportion (20.00%) attained scores in the "Very Good" range (25-32), while a smaller segment (25.00%) remained in the "Poor" range (9-16). The calculated mean posttest score of 20.05, interpreted as Good, suggests that the control group experienced some degree of knowledge retention or improvement in the assessed mathematical concepts between the pretest and posttest, despite not being subjected to the experimental intervention.

Table 2. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Control Group in their Pretest in terms of Knowledge Retention

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	
33 – 40	0	0.00	0	0.00	Excellent
25 – 32	0	0.00	4	20.00	Very Good
17 – 24	5	25.00	11	55.00	Good
9 – 16	15	75.00	5	25.00	Poor
0 – 8	0	0.00	0	0.00	Very Poor
Mean Score (Pretest)			15.05		Poor
Mean Score (Posttest)			20.05		Good

2. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pretest and Posttest

2.1. Student Engagement

The students' mathematics performance in the experimental group was positively influenced by the implemented intervention. By comparing the students' overall scores in the pretest (2.42) and posttest (3.19), the results showed a significant improvement as scores shifted from "Not Engaged" to "Engaged". This also stipulates that the implementation of the relay teaching method created positive changes in how students engage in mathematics.

Table 3. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Experimental Group in their Pretest and Posttest in terms of Student Engagement

Statement		Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation	
1.	I listen to my teacher in my math class.	Pretest	2.70	2	Engaged
		Posttest	3.55	2	Highly Engaged
2.	I participate in the discussion in math class.	Pretest	2.45	12	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.45	3.5	Engaged
3.	I work hard in math class.	Pretest	2.65	3.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.45	3.5	Engaged
4.	At home, I review math problems that I did not understand in school.	Pretest	2.20	21	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.30	14.5	Engaged
5.	When I make mistakes in math, I work until I correct them.	Pretest	2.50	9.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.40	6.5	Engaged
6.	I follow my teacher's directions in math class.	Pretest	2.75	1	Engaged
		Posttest	3.60	1	Highly Engaged
7.	I sometimes act out as if I am studying in math class. \mathbb{R}	Pretest	2.10	24	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.80	21.5	Engaged
8.	I am interested in learning new things in math.	Pretest	2.40	14	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.35	10.5	Engaged
9.	I do like attending math classes.	Pretest	2.35	16	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.30	14.5	Engaged
10.	Learning math is fun.	Pretest	2.60	5.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.35	10.5	Engaged
11.	I feel excited when I study in math.	Pretest	2.45	12	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.40	6.5	Engaged
12.	I feel bored when I study in math. \mathbb{R}	Pretest	2.65	3.5	Engaged
		Posttest	1.90	25	Not Engaged
13.	I am excited about solving difficult math problems.	Pretest	2.45	12	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.25	17	Engaged
14.	I want to spend more time solving math problems.	Pretest	2.55	7.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.35	10.5	Engaged

15.	I want to get good grade in math class.	Pretest	2.55	7.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.40	6.5	Engaged
16.	When I study math, I ask myself questions to make sure I understand it correctly.	Pretest	2.60	5.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.20	18.5	Engaged
17.	I try to connect math to real-life situations.	Pretest	2.30	19	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.75	23	Engaged
18.	I try to think of different ways to solve math problems.	Pretest	2.30	19	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.40	6.5	Engaged
19.	I try to develop my own strategy when I solve math problems.	Pretest	2.35	16	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.05	20	Engaged
20.	I set a goal for myself when I study math.	Pretest	2.35	16	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.05	21.5	Engaged
21.	When I can't solve a math problem, I try to change my strategy.	Pretest	2.15	22.5	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.30	14.5	Engaged
22.	I often think about something else when I study math. \mathbb{R}	Pretest	2.50	9.5	Engaged
		Posttest	3.30	14.5	Engaged
23.	At home, I think about what I learned in math class.	Pretest	2.30	19	Not Engaged
		Posttest	2.55	24	Engaged
24.	I am focused when I study math.	Pretest	2.15	22.5	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.35	10.5	Engaged
25.	I memorized important facts to understand math better.	Pretest	2.05	25	Not Engaged
		Posttest	3.20	18.5	Engaged
Overall Mean (Pretest)			2.42		Not Engaged
Overall Mean (Posttest)			3.19		Engaged

2.2. Knowledge Retention

Initially, the experimental group's pretest scores averaged 15.60, showing that their knowledge retention was at a generally poor level of performance. Specifically, most students, about 65%, scored between 9 and 16, putting them in the Poor category. On the other hand, 35% scored between 17 and 24, which is considered Good. It is important to note that no one scored in the Excellent, Very Good, or Very Poor categories. With a mean score of 15.60, the overall performance clearly indicates that these students had a limited grasp of math concepts before the conduct of the study. However, the results of the posttest for the experimental group show a clear enhancement in math knowledge retention, with their overall performance rated as Very Good. A substantial proportion of the students achieved scores within the "Very Good" range (35.00%) and the "Good" range (45.00%). Furthermore, a segment of the experimental group exhibited "Excellent" knowledge retention (10.00%). A small portion of students (10.00%) scored in the "Poor" category, and none in the "Very Poor" category. The computed average post-test score of 25.10 supports this positive line of trend, which also falls into "Very good" interpretation.

Table 4. Level of Mathematics Performance of the Experimental Group in their Pretest and Posttest in terms of Knowledge Retention

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	
33 – 40	0	0.00	0	0.00	Excellent
25 – 32	0	0.00	2	10.00	Very Good
17 – 24	7	35.00	9	35.00	Good
9 – 16	13	65.00	7	45.00	Poor
0 – 8	0	0.00	2	10.00	Very Poor
Mean Score (Pretest)			15.60	Poor	
Mean Score (Posttest)			25.10	Very Good	

3. Difference between the Pretest Scores of the Control Group and Experimental Group

The comparison of the pretest scores aims to determine if the students in the two groups under study are relatively similar. This is important as it establishes that the respondents in either group are relatively homogenous in pre-intervention levels of mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention.

The computed U-value of 213.50 and a p-value of 0.718 with a significance level of 0.05, which shows a non-significant difference amongst the level of mathematics performance of the students using the conventional and relay teaching methods in terms of student engagement, before employing the intervention in either group.

Table 5. Analysis of Pretest Scores of Students in Conventional and Relay Teaching Methods in terms of Student Engagement

Student Engagement	Observation	Mean	U	p-value	Interpretation
Conventional Teaching Method	20	2.41	213.50	0.718	Not significant
Relay Teaching Method	20	2.42			

Legend: p-value < 0.05 = Significant

Likewise, a computed U-value of 230.50 and a p-value of 0.414 with a significance level of 0.05, which indicates a non-significant difference among the level of mathematics performance of the students using the conventional and relay teaching methods in terms of knowledge retention, before employing the intervention in either group.

Table 6. Analysis of Pretest Scores of Students in Conventional and Relay Teaching Methods in terms of Knowledge Retention

Knowledge Retention	Observation	Mean	U	p-value	Interpretation
Conventional Teaching Method	20	15.05	230.50	0.414	Not significant
Relay Teaching Method	20	15.60			

Legend: p-value < 0.05 = Significant

4. Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control Group

In terms of student engagement, the computed W-value of 210.00 and a p-value of 0.001 are significant at the significance level of 0.05. Similarly, in terms of knowledge retention, the computed W-value of 189.00 and a p-value of 0.001 are significant at the level of significance of 0.05.

Table 7. Analysis of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students in Conventional Teaching Method in terms of Student Engagement

Conventional	Observation	Mean	W	p-value	Interpretation
Pretest	20	2.41	210.00	0.001	Significant
Posttest	20	2.89			

Legend: p-value < 0.05 = Significant

Table 8. Analysis of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students in Conventional Teaching Method in terms of Knowledge Retention

Conventional	Observation	Mean	W	p-value	Interpretation
Pretest	20	15.05	189.00	0.001	Significant
Posttest	20	20.05			

Legend: p-value < 0.05 = Significant

5. Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

The computed W-value of 210.00 and a p-value of 0.001 are significant at the significance level of 0.05. This demonstrates a significant difference between the level of mathematics performance of the students in terms of student engagement before and after employing the relay teaching method. Correspondingly, the computed W-value of 209.00 and a p-value of 0.001 are significant at the level of significance of 0.05.

Table 9. Analysis of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students in Relay Teaching Method in terms of Student Engagement

Relay Teaching	Observation	Mean	W	p-value	Interpretation
Pretest	20	2.42	210.00	0.001	Significant
Posttest	20	3.19			

Legend: $p\text{-value} < 0.05 = \text{Significant}$

Table 10. Analysis of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students in Relay Teaching Method in terms of Knowledge Retention

Relay Teaching	Observation	Mean	W	p-value	Interpretation
Pretest	20	15.60	209.00	0.001	Significant
Posttest	20	25.10			

Legend: $p\text{-value} < 0.05 = \text{Significant}$

6. Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Control Group and Experimental Group

In terms of student engagement, the computed U-value of 344.50 and a p-value of 0.001 are significant at the significance level of 0.05. This indicates a significant difference between the posttest scores in terms of student engagement of the students belonging to the control group using the conventional teaching method and the students belonging to the experimental group using the relay teaching method.

Table 11. Analysis of Posttest Scores of Students in Conventional and Relay Teaching Methods in terms of Student Engagement

Student Engagement	Observation	Mean	U	p-value	Interpretation
Conventional Teaching Method	20	2.89	344.50	0.001	Significant
Relay Teaching Method	20	3.19			

Legend: $p\text{-value} < 0.05 = \text{Significant}$

On the other hand, in terms of knowledge retention, the computed U-value of 317.50 and a p-value of 0.001 at the significance level of 0.05 show a significant difference in the posttest scores of the control group using the conventional teaching method and the experimental group using the relay teaching method.

Table 12. Analysis of Posttest Scores of Students in Conventional and Relay Teaching Methods in terms of Knowledge Retention

Knowledge Retention	Observation	Mean	U	p-value	Interpretation
Conventional Teaching Method	20	20.05	317.50	0.001	Significant
Relay Teaching Method	20	25.10			

Legend: $p\text{-value} < 0.05 = \text{Significant}$

7. Proposed Course Enhancement Plan to Enhance the Students' Mathematics Performance

The proposed course plan uses the relay-teaching method, which will serve as a guide for the relay teachers. The course plan is thoughtfully structured around a clearly defined course description, course outcomes, resource materials, and assessments. With the proposed course plan for Research Statistics, the instructors may choose the applicable teaching strategies and activities for their teaching and learning process.

Table 13. Proposed Course Enhancement Plan

COURSE TITLE: RESEARCH STATISTICS						
This course provides a basic understanding of the concept of probability theory and statistical inference, which are necessary to employ statistical methods effectively in business situations. Topics covered are statistical estimation, hypothesis testing, and statistical analyses using software. An expected output of the course is the ability to use statistical presentation to aid in reporting information, such as histograms, pie charts, ogives, pictograms, and polygons.						
COURSE CODE: OEO04						
CREDIT UNITS: 3 units						
PREREQUISITES: GEO03						
COURSE OUTCOMES:						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Demonstrate a solid understanding of basic statistical concepts. b. Possess the knowledge and skills to strategically select, implement, and critically evaluate sampling methods in diverse research contexts. c. Develop skills employing statistical techniques to test hypotheses and analyze data in business situations using statistical methods and software. d. Use statistical presentation as an aid to reporting information 						
COURSE OUTLINE						
Week	Desired Learning Outcomes	Course Content	Textbooks/References	Teaching/Learning Activities	Resource Materials	Assessment

1	<p>1. Internalize the Vision and Mission of OMSC and contribute to the realization of CBAM's goals and BSBA objectives</p> <p>2. Demonstrate awareness of GAD and Juvenile Delinquency Awareness</p>	<p>Orientation of students</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMSC Vision and Mission • CBAM Goals BSBA Objectives • Gender and Development: Juvenile Delinquency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • College Code Administrative Manual • RA 9344 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An interactive discussion and brainstorming activity about the VMGO and Core Values and GAD: Juvenile Delinquency (R.A. 9344) 	<p>Guide Questions</p> <p>Laptop</p>	<p>Assessment 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students share their thoughts by writing a reflection about the topic. <p>Assessment 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slogan-making activity about Juvenile Delinquency (R.A. 9344) to promote awareness
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RELAY TEACHING METHOD						
CO1: Demonstrate a solid understanding of basic statistical concepts.						
2	<p>1. Demonstrate understanding of statistics, types of research, variables, their diverse types, and various levels of meas</p>	<p>1. Basic Concepts in Statistical Methods</p> <p>a. Definition of Statistics</p> <p>b. Definition and Types of Research</p> <p>c. Types of Variables and Data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nauhar, Manoj (2022). Fundamentals of statistics. Arcler Press. ▪ Jain, S. (2019). Research methodology in arts, science and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion about the brief history of statistics and its types and classifications. • Introduction to basic statistical terms and concepts. • Discussion about the examples of nominal, ordinal, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power Point Presentation • Laptop • Visual Aids 	<p>Assessment 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short quiz on defining statistics, the importance of statistics, and classification of variables. <p>Assessment 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual activity about the differentiation of descriptive and

	urement. 2. Explore the roles of statistics in the development of knowledge and everyday life.	d. Role of Statistics	humanities.	interval, and ratio data as levels of measurement.		inferential statistics.
CO2: Possess the knowledge and skills to strategically select, implement, and critically evaluate sampling methods in diverse research contexts.						
3-4	1. Illustrate a comprehensive understanding of the distinction between populations and samples, various sampling techniques, and data collection and organization	2. Population and Sampling a. Population and Sample b. Determining sample Size c. Data Collection and Sampling Techniques d. Frequency Distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nauhw ar, Manoj (2022). Fundamental of statistics. Arcler Press. ▪ Jain, S. (2019). Research methodology in arts, science, and humanities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion about the different sampling techniques. • Brainstorming activity about population and sampling. • Discuss and determine the parts of the frequency distribution table. • Lecture about how to fill out the frequency distribution table by 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power Point Presentation • Laptop Visual aids 	<p>Assessment 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compute the sample size of the given population (N) using Sloven's Formula (<i>board work</i>) <p>Assessment 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual activity about the commonly used sampling techniques. <p>Assessment 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual activity on frequency distribution table.

	n methods.			following certain steps		Assessment 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective-type assessment
	2. Construct a frequency distribution table					
	3. Apply the concepts related to population and sampling to different real world scenarios.					
CO3: Develop skills employing statistical techniques to test hypotheses and analyze data in business situations using statistical methods and software.						
5-8	1. Exemplify proficiency in solving problems related to measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion, and measures of position	1. Descriptive Statistics <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Measures of Central Tendency: Mean, Median, Mode, Trimmed Mean, Weighted Mean 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nauhar, Manoj (2022). Fundamental of statistics. Arcler Press. Jain, S. (2019). Research methodology in arts, science and humanities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multimedia Instruction (Video Viewing) Discuss how to compute the mean, median, mode, and quantiles of the ungrouped and grouped data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Television Power Point Presentation Video Clips Research Statistics Module 	Assessment 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual activity about computing the mean, median, mode, range, variance, standard deviation, and quantiles of a given data set.

CO3: Develop skills employing statistical techniques to test hypotheses and analyze data in business situations using statistical methods and software.						
5-8	2. Recognize the application of the measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion, and measures of position to practical situations.	b. Measure of Dispersion: Range, Variance, Standard Deviation c. Measure of Position: Quartiles, Percentiles, Deciles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prieto, N. G. (2017). Practical research quantitative 2nd Edition 119 – 139 pages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussion on how to compute the range, mean deviation, standard deviation, and variance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Television Power Point Presentation Video Clips Research Statistics Module 	Assessment 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Board work. Assessment 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective-type assessment
9	Written Examination (Midterm)					
CO3: Develop skills employing statistical techniques to test hypotheses and analyze data in business situations using statistical methods and software.						
10-11	1. Demonstrate proficiency in hypothesis testing by identifying various types	4. Hypothesis Testing <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Types of Hypothesis Type I & II Errors Steps for Hypothesis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nauhar, Manoj (2022). Fundamental of statistics. Arcler Press. Jain, S. (2019). Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An interactive discussion on hypothesis testing and its types with the use of mathematical games. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laptop/Computer Power Point Presentation Video Clips Microsoft Excel SPSS 	Assessment 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Think-Pair-Share on formulating null and alternative hypotheses. Assessment 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate correctness in identifying null and

	<p>of hypotheses, errors, and levels of significance.</p> <p>2. Familiarize with the steps of hypothesis testing.</p> <p>3. Differentiate a one-tailed test from a two-tailed test.</p> <p>4. Listing the sequential steps involved in hypothesis testing.</p>	<p>Testing</p> <p>d. Level of Significance</p> <p>e. One-tailed and Two-tailed Tests</p>	<p>ch methodology in arts, science and humanities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amin, T. T. (2019). Inferential Statistics. <i>Cairo University</i>. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.26024.62725. Prieto, N. G. (2017). Practical research quantitative 2nd Edition 119 – 139pages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-World Scenarios or Intuition Focus on the “Why” Scenario Sorting Activity; the students will identify the if the given scenario is a null or alternative hypothesis. 	<p>alternative hypotheses, including directional (one-tailed) vs. non-directional (two-tailed) alternatives.</p> <p>Assessment 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Worksheets about classifying errors and justifying their answers. <p>Assessment 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective-type quiz about the types of hypotheses, errors, and levels of significance.
<p>CO3: Develop skills employing statistical techniques to test hypotheses and analyze data in business situations using statistical methods and software.</p>					
<p>12-15</p>	<p>1. Display mastery in</p>	<p>Statistical Analysis</p> <p>a. T-Tests</p> <p>b. One-Way</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amin, T. T. (2019). Inferential Statistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multimedia Instruction (Video Viewing) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laptop/Computer Power Point <p>Assessment 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective-type assessment

	<p>identifying which statistical method to use in a particular data set.</p> <p>2. Compute the t-value and f-value for the t-test and ANOVA.</p> <p>3. Interpret the result of a statistical analysis.</p> <p>4. Exhibit proficiency in using Microsoft Excel and SPSS in analyzing data.</p>	<p>ANOVA A c. Correlation</p> <p>Statistical Analysis using Software</p> <p>a. MS Excel b. SPSS</p>	<p>cs. Cairo University. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.26024.62725.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nauhar, Manoj (2022). <i>Fundamental of statistics</i>. Arcler Press. Jain, S. (2019). <i>Research methodology in arts, science and humanities</i>. Amin, T. T. (2019). <i>Inferential Statistics</i>. Cairo University. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.26024.62725. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussion about different statistical analysis and its interpretation. Analyzing and interpreting data with the use of different statistical methods. Interactive discussion by utilizing mathematical games. Hands-on laboratory activity on the use of statistical software 	<p>Presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Video Clips Microsoft Excel SPSS Research papers 	<p>Assessment 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graded oral recitation evaluating the students' mastery in identifying the appropriate statistical test for a particular study. <p>Assessment 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Board work. <p>Assessment 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rubrics assessment for activities employing the use of statistical software - Microsoft Excel and SPSS.
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prieto, N. G. (2017). Practical research quantitative 2nd Edition 119 – 139pages 			
CO4: Use statistical presentation as an aid to reporting information						
16-17	<p>Demonstrate proficiency in a statistical presentation by :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying which type of data presentation is appropriate for a particular data, as an aid to reporting information. Presenting data using differ 	<p>5. Statistical Presentation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Types data presentation: Textual, Tabular, Graphical Histogram Pie Charts Ogives Pictograms Polygons. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nauhar, Manoj (2022). Fundamental of statistics. Arcler Press Jain, S. (2019). Research methodology in arts, science and humanities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brainstorming activity about the appropriate statistical presentation Class discussion on the types of data presentation Creation of students' statistical presentation Data Presentation Detective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laptop/Computer Power Point Presentation Video Clips Microsoft Excel SPSS Research papers 	<p>Assessment 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rubrics will be used to evaluate the group's use of statistical presentation as an aid to reporting information. <p>Assessment 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short quiz about types of statistical presentation in presenting data. <p>Assessment 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Presentation Detective <p>Assessment 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build Your Own Histogram <p>Assessment 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pie Chart Party

	ent types of statistical presentation.					Assessment 6 • Ogive Construction Challenge
18	Written Examination (Final Term)					
SUGGESTED LEARNING RESOURCES:						
Electronic Resources:						
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>How to Use SPSS - An Introduction to SPSS for Beginners.</i> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_zFBUfZEBWQ&list=PLVI_iGT5ZuRkk2d-kePUMlHD5pmOuquN 2. <i>Statistical Tools for Research.</i> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6lkDpvd99_o 3. <i>Statistics made easy!!! Learn about the t-test, the chi square test, the p value and more.</i> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l10q6fjPxJ0 4. Moreira, Olga (Ed). (2023). Advanced techniques for collecting statistical data. Arcler Press. https://portal.igpublish.com.library.omsc.edu.ph/iglibrary/obj/ARCLER0001189?searchid=16867133144701CtTfcAlb~IlcSIVYQNNk 5. Nauhwar, Manoj (2022). Fundamental of statistics. Arcler Press. https://portal.igpublish.com.library.omsc.edu.ph/iglibrary/obj/ARCLER0001048?searchid=1686712791819BjQgVk6PhyrCQN2ZKI6Qs 6. Jain, S. (2019). Research methodology in arts, science and humanities. Society Publishing. https://portal.igpublish.com.library.omsc.edu.ph/iglibrary/obj/ARCLER0000412?searchid=1686805386564Gui0TbIOOHcTymigvbFwz 7. Jain, S. (2019). Research methods for modern business environment. Society Publishing. https://portal.igpublish.com.library.omsc.edu.ph/iglibrary/obj/ARCLER0000549?searchid=1686805839209gFBZVVmhpAlsDlwMygElw 8. Montemar, Claire (2019). Probability theory and examples. Arcler Press. 9. https://portal.igpublish.com.library.omsc.edu.ph/iglibrary/reader/ARCLER0000182/1 						
Teachery Bank						
(Teachers may scan the QR code to access teaching resources.)						
Prepared by:						
ANDREA MAE H. URBANO						
Professional Lecturer						

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows an improvement and shifted the students' engagement from "Not Engaged" to "Engaged", which indicates that the implementation of the conventional teaching positively influenced the way the students engage and participate in mathematics. To substantiate the idea, it is highlighted in several studies that while traditional teaching methods in mathematics are often characterized by teacher-centered lectures and rote memorization, they also present notable limitations compared to more interactive, student-centered approaches. Traditionally, lecture-based teaching, having one teacher to deliver instruction, remains prevalent in mathematics classrooms worldwide. This approach can foster certain aspects of engagement, particularly for students motivated by grades or external rewards (Akpalu et al., 2025). However, such engagement often leans toward compliance and extrinsic motivation rather than genuine interest in developing their strategy for solving or the enjoyment of mathematics. While students may not report high levels of boredom, as evident with the data above, this does not necessarily equate to deep or active engagement with mathematical concepts (Lee & Paul, 2023).

Table 2 indicates that the control group experienced some degree of knowledge retention or improvement in the assessed mathematical concepts between the pretest and posttest, despite not being subjected to the experimental intervention. These findings align with some studies on mathematics, which state that learning retention consistently reports that, even without experimental interventions, students often maintain a significant portion of their acquired knowledge in the short term, particularly on factual and procedural tasks. A study by Valderama and Oligo (2021), which employed a pretest and posttest design, found that learners retained approximately 78% of mathematical knowledge over seven weeks, though retention declined gradually at an average rate of 3% per week. This suggests that some improvement or maintenance of performance in control groups is plausible, especially if the posttest occurs relatively soon after the initial learning phase. Therefore, while the reported posttest results for the control group indicate some degree of retention and improvement, these gains may not persist over longer intervals or for more complex mathematical concepts without additional instructional support.

Based on the results shown in Table 3, the implementation of the relay teaching method created positive changes in how students engage in mathematics. To support the claim, research conducted by Taban et al. (2023) investigated the impact of relay teaching on college students' mathematics performance and engagement. They adopted a pretest and posttest mode and discovered that the students performed better after the application of relay teaching. Students also expressed a sense of increased motivation and engagement in math courses. According to students, this technique brought lessons alive and motivated them to become more involved. The research also pointed out that relay teaching helps maintain student interest. The findings showed that relay teaching,

when paired with extra learning activities, proves successful in boosting both math performance and student engagement.

Table 4 shows that the use of the relay teaching method significantly improved the students' ability to retain information on the mathematical concepts. Current research backs up the idea that employing an intervention helps has a how well students remember math concepts, which shows up in better scores on tests after the lessons. A quasi-experimental study by Alviar and Gamorez (2024) showed that utilizing an interactive learning and teaching instruction led to a higher mathematics performance compared to traditional classes. Similarly, Lehtikoinen et al. (2025) revealed that the group of students who received co-teaching showed more improvement in mathematics grades compared to solo-teaching groups. The study also suggests that co-teaching may lead to increased cognitive engagement, potentially translating to better achievement. However, contradictory evidence comes from Engle (2022), who found no statistically significant difference in long-term knowledge retention between students engaged in a collaborative teaching method and those using traditional retrieval activities, although some subgroups benefited more from specific methods. This indicates that while interventions can be effective, their impact may vary based on student characteristics and the nature of the retrieval activity.

Table 5 and Table 6 show that initially, the respondents from both groups have a similar level of mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention; both groups performed poorly. These indicate the homogeneity of the respondents. It is essential to test the homogeneity of the respondents before the intervention to ensure that the respondents have a reasonably similar level of mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention. This ensures that improvements in students' math performance can be linked to the use of the intervention, not to other factors related to students' existing skills or traits (Cabrestante & Lopez, 2023).

As shown in Table 7, the conventional teaching method yields significant improvement in students' participation in mathematics. This improvement in engagement is important since it can lead to improved understanding and academic performance. However, while the conventional teaching method may promote participation, several studies have established that collaborative teaching methods, such as relay teaching, typically have a greater effect on student engagement (Norton, 2024). Concisely, though conventional teaching may offer improvements in students' mathematics performance, there is a lack of proof to substantiate the claim that conventional teaching improves student engagement. As claimed by several studies, alternative teaching approaches are consistently proven effective in enhancing engagement and participation in mathematics (Galvan et al., 2024).

In Table 8, the results reveal that the conventional method of instruction enhances knowledge retention in mathematics among students. Even though other methods like relay teaching may have meaningful advantages, the conventional method is somehow relevant in improving knowledge retention in mathematics among students. The result can be associated with the study of Norton (2024), which asserted that conventional teaching methods can help students retain knowledge with proper instructions, implementation, and guided practice. In addition, the study also claimed that conventional teaching remains relevant in different classrooms, as it provides students with a foundation for learning with the help of regular practice. On the contrary, as stated by the study of Ihendinihu (2020), the conventional teaching method isn't always better for retaining knowledge; it may provide a difference in students' scores, but not better than using a collaborative teaching method. In conclusion, even though conventional teaching has its benefits, it should not be seen as the preeminent approach to enhance students' retention of mathematical concepts (Mosia & Egara, 2024).

The results in Table 9 conclusively show that the relay teaching method greatly improves student engagement in mathematics. To substantiate the idea, studies have shown that students instructed with the relay teaching method, which involves different teachers teaching the course per session, improve significantly on their before and after test scores in mathematics (Taban et al., 2023). While cited studies show a clear implication of the relay teaching method in students' improved performance, it did not provide strong evidence to show its impact on student engagement. However, it is widely believed that higher engagement is usually associated with improved learning outcomes, which implies that this teaching method effectively engages and stimulates students in learning as it improves students' performance (Chui & Chui, 2024). Hence, we can conclude that if relay teaching improves mathematics performance, and so does student engagement, and this enhanced engagement can lead to positively developed performance and a meaningful understanding of mathematical concepts (Lee & Paul, 2023).

Table 10 indicates that the relay teaching method is effective in improving students' knowledge retention. The improvement in students' pretest and posttest scores following the intervention suggests that this collaborative, multi-teacher method can produce significant learning gains over the baseline performance before its implementation. In support of this, the study of Taban et al. (2023) concluded that the relay teaching method remarkably improved the students' mathematics performance. Specifically, the findings indicate that relay teaching can effectively aid students' retention of statistical ideas. The same study also suggested that relay teaching can be supplemented with enrichment activities such as coaching, sharing of lecture notes, and integration of social media, which would help further support students' knowledge retention. On the other hand, the claim contradicts the study of Freeman et al. (2022), which states that the use of the relay method might be engaging, but it does not directly support learning retention. These findings demonstrate that methods such as relay teaching, which is an active and

collaborative approach, might have the potential to enhance students' mathematics performance in terms of knowledge retention, but their effectiveness hinges on implementation and context (Conway, 2015).

Evidently, the findings in Table 11 show that the relay teaching method has a more significant impact on enhancing student engagement than the conventional teaching method. The findings were affirmed by the study of Zhang et al. (2024), which attests that teaching approaches like relay teaching directly enhance student engagement. It has been proven that teaching methods that promote interaction, cooperation, and engagement contribute to the increased level of student engagement in class compared to conventional passive teaching approaches. In terms of the stated results, they show that there is a higher level of involvement of students when using the relay teaching method in comparison to the conventional method of teaching, which greatly supports the claim that it has an effect on student engagement management.

Table 12 implies that the relay teaching method improves the students' mathematics performance in terms of knowledge retention. In conclusion, the relay teaching method is effective in helping students retain statistical concepts compared to the conventional teaching method. As it was stated, math retention among students was improved by cooperative teaching, which in turn led to students' achievements in math (Eze, 2024). The study also recommended that the collaboration of teachers in delivering instructions can be applied in teaching mathematics. In conclusion, the aforementioned pieces of evidence indicate that both the cooperative teaching method and the relay teaching method positively impacted the students' performance in mathematics and statistics, including their ability to remember information, compared to traditional methods.

Based on the results of the study, a course enhancement plan has been proposed. The plan includes various teaching methods like direct instruction, visuals, real-world examples, and think-pair-share to cater to different learning styles. This flexibility helps teachers adjust their approach based on what students need and making learning more engaging. Also, using the relay-teaching method, multiple teachers will share the teaching responsibilities for each session. When several teachers get involved, students get to see different ways of teaching and real-life examples. This diversity makes it easier for every student to learn and understand statistical ideas concepts.

Additionally, teachers may utilize instructional materials made by other teachers by scanning the QR code provided, and they may also share their learning resources to effectively aid the students' learning. This supports the recommendations of the study of Taban et al. (2023), which highlighted that the use of the relay teaching method could be more effective with enrichment activities such as coaching and sharing of lecture notes, and the use of social media and the internet.

Overall, the proposed course enhancement plan for the Research Statistics course makes things more engaging and helps students learn better. Relay teaching allows

teachers to work together and keeps students interested and engaged. By combining different teaching strategies and assessments, this approach helps students develop the skills they need for analyzing data in research and business context. The traditional statistics courses typically present theories and concepts extensively without providing students with practical experience to develop their hands-on skills. The course enhancement plan for Research Statistics aims to effectively employ statistical methods in the business field and analyze data in situations using statistical methods and software. This addresses students who possess theoretical knowledge yet face difficulties when they attempt to apply their understanding to real datasets.

Moreover, by incorporating real-world scenarios in the teaching strategy, students move beyond rote memorization and help them to deeply understand the concepts behind the underlying principles. In terms of the activities in this course plan, such as Think-Pair-Share, Scenario-Sorting Activity, and hands-on data analysis using software, Mathematics teachers will promote student engagement and active participation. This course enhancement plan also allows flexibility to its users by adapting and adjusting their strategies and assessments to meet the students' needs and interests. Overall, the course enhancement plan ensures that the students will develop not just computational skills but also critical thinking skills, which are necessary for effective data analysis in the business field.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The use of a conventional teaching method improved the students' mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention.
2. The use of the relay teaching method notably improved the students' mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention.
3. The mathematical performance of students in both the control group and the experimental group showed no differences concerning student engagement and knowledge retention. This indicates that the groups were comparable before the intervention.
4. The students' level of mathematics performance in terms of student engagement and knowledge retention has increased compared to their performance before employing the conventional teaching method.
5. The students' performance in mathematics regarding engagement and retention of knowledge has increased compared to their performance before employing the relay teaching method.
6. Students taught using the relay teaching method exceeded the mathematics performance of the students who received the traditional teaching approach regarding their engagement and knowledge retention. This suggests that incorporating relay teaching can effectively improve mathematics performance compared to conventional teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is strongly recommended that mathematics teachers blend collaborative teaching methods, such as relay teaching and team teaching, with conventional approaches to further improve student performance. These collaborative strategies actively engage students, boost participation, and enhance knowledge retention. To maximize the benefits of the relay teaching method, teachers should incorporate enrichment activities like coaching sessions, sharing lecture notes, and integrating technology, while continuously refining instructional strategies to emphasize deep conceptual understanding rather than rote memorization.

Furthermore, teachers are encouraged to maintain effective conventional teaching practices that promote student engagement and positive assessment outcomes. Given the observed improvements in student involvement and retention through relay teaching, its strategic integration into mathematics instruction is highly advised.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, it is equally important that ethical implications are considered. Respondents were fully informed about the aim of the study, what their involvement entails, and how their data would be used. The respondents' participation was completely voluntary, and they could decide not to answer questions or continue participating at any time without penalty. Respondents' anonymity was kept by not disclosing the information collected from the students to anyone, and by using the data for academic purposes only. Additionally, informed consent was sought from each respondent before commencing the study, which provided respect and safety for the respondents to share their experiences.

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